

ANALYSIS OF CARBON FIBER COMPOSITE ELECTRODE

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ABSTRACT

In this article a novel energy-storing composite electrode is investigated with regards to its mechanical and electrochemical properties. This composite electrode consists of carbon fibers, which provide both the mechanical reinforcement and the negative electrode in the battery cell. Also, this carbon fiber composite electrode consists of a polymer matrix that can conduct lithium ions, in order to simultaneously act as the electrolyte in the battery cell.

Electrochemical tests were performed on the manufactured composite electrode and show extremely promising results for the battery performance. Furthermore, mechanical tests show that the composite electrode has acceptable mechanical properties for structural use.

It is shown that the internal distances in the composite are large, and volume fraction of fibers is low. This is not only significantly limiting the mechanical properties of the composite, but also the electrochemical properties.

Overall, the carbon fiber composite electrode is found to have suitable characteristics for further research, where many further research topics are found in order to improve and characterize the composite further.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites have widespread use in structural components, in a wide variety of products as a means to reduce weight. With increasing use of electric vehicles, further weight reduction can be imagined using energy-storing composites, also called structural battery. This composite is a multifunctional component which both store electrical energy and carry mechanical load.

This article investigates the properties of such novel carbon fiber composite electrode. The composite electrode is constructed from combining the theory of composites with lithium-ion battery to create the fundamentally new multifunctional material.

When manufacturing such a material it is extremely challenging to reach the typical properties of an epoxy-based composite or the typical properties of a conventional lithium battery. Instead, observing the material as used at a system-level, large reduction in mass of the whole system can be achieved, when essentially eliminating the need for separate batteries.

As known in composites, it is necessary to have a matrix material to distribute the load between the reinforcing fibers. However, when constructing a composite electrode an additional requirement is applied. Since the matrix also acts as the electrolyte in the battery cell it has to conduct lithium-ions. Thus, the polymeric material is performing both the tasks of the matrix and the electrolyte, and is therefore multifunctional. Herein this matrix material is referred to as Solid Polymer Electrolyte (SPE).

Furthermore, for the battery to function, the material has to contain a positive and a negative electrode. In conventional lithium-ion batteries, the negative electrode consists of graphite powder adhered to a copper foil. It is thus not unlikely to assume carbon fibers would function satisfactory as well. Previous work has shown that carbon fibers work well as the negative electrode in a lithium-ion battery cell [1]. Also, it has been shown that the mechanical properties of the carbon fibers remain relatively unchanged for up to 1000 charging cycles [2]. With the carbon fibers performing both the task of reinforcement in the composite, as well as being the negative electrode in the battery, the carbon fibers themselves are multifunctional.

Both the carbon fibers and the SPE do therefore appear suitable for a structural battery. Combining the constituents into a carbon fiber composite electrode is thus creating an overall multifunctional material; one that can intrinsically both take mechanical load and store electrical energy. However, little is known on the subject of the properties for the carbon fiber composite electrode. Therefore, the emphasis in this work lies in the investigation of mechanical and electrochemical properties of this carbon fiber composite electrode.

2 METHOD

A novel SPE is synthesized to solve the challenge of having a solid matrix that at the same time function as an electrolyte. The SPE material is manufactured both as a bulk material, and molded with carbon fibers in a unidirectional carbon fiber composite lamina. The lamina is made from spread tow carbon fibers of the type *Toray T800HB-6k-40B*, where the spread tow carbon fibers are taped to a glass panel, and the monomer and electrolyte mixture is applied to the fibers by hand. Another glass panel is applied on top and the panels are clamped together. This is left in ambient light for 1 minute, and then cured under 100 W *Blak-Ray B-100AP* mercury UV-light (365 nm) for 3.5 minutes, providing an intensity of 16 mW/cm² at the sample. The finished lamina is carefully removed from the glass panels and used for either mechanical or electrochemical tests.

The carbon fiber to SPE contact is of definitive significance for the mechanical properties of a composite in order to transfer loads between the fibers. Within a structural battery, the interface has a second competing property, which is the electrochemical contact between the electrolyte and the carbon fiber. If any of these competing properties outdo the other in physical contact to the carbon fibers, the multifunctionality of the material is lost.

In order to verify the electrochemical properties of the carbon fiber composite electrode, and the ionic contact of the SPE to the carbon fibers, electrochemical cycling (controlled charge and discharge) of the composite electrode is performed. This is made with a Potentiostat on the composite electrode cycled at $C/20$, which means a theoretical full charge is reached after 20 hours. For testing electrochemical conductivity of the SPE, a conductivity-testing rig is used.

For investigating the mechanical properties of the carbon fiber composite electrode, the tests have been divided into testing bulk material properties and composite lamina properties. Bulk properties are tested with both DMTA testing, and tensile testing with Deben 300 N tensile tester. The tensile tester also provides the ultimate tensile strength of the polymer.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Bulk SPE Characteristics

The bulk elastic modulus of the SPE was measured to 600 MPa on average and the ultimate tensile strength was 9 MPa , where variations are very dependent on the monomer mixing and curing time.

Furthermore, the SPE electrochemical conductivity was measured to about $3 \cdot 10^{-4}\text{ S/cm}$, which is extremely promising for the ion conductivity within the battery. This value highly depends on the monomer mixing and curing time as well.

The uncertainty of the properties is due to difficulties in controlling the manufacturing process, resulting in bulk materials with slightly varying mechanical and electrochemical properties. With lower mechanical properties, the conductivity of the matrix increases, and vice-versa, which also means that the final properties can be tailored according to need.

3.2 Composite Characteristics

The electrochemical cycling was performed for 10 cycles, where the capacity was measured to around 180 mAh/g as shown in Figure 1a. The theoretical maximum capacity for graphite is 372 mAh/g , and theoretical value for the carbon fibers is expected close to this value. Furthermore, the Coulombic efficiency of the cell was calculated to 98.87% as shown in Figure 1b. This Coulombic efficiency is not acceptable for commercial use. However, tests have shown that carbon fibers can reach extremely high Coulombic efficiency, which leads to the conclusion that the Coulombic efficiency found here is likely due to the SPE. It is possible chemical side reactions occur or it is due to large internal distances within the battery cell. Further research is necessary in order to improve the Coulombic efficiency.

Figure 1a: Electrochemical capacity for the composite electrode.

Figure 1b: Coulombic efficiency for the composite electrode.

For both higher mechanical properties of the carbon fiber composite electrode, as well as better electrochemical properties, the fiber volume fraction of the composite is of high importance. An optical microscope was used in order to examine the carbon fibers and SPE in the composite. Figure 2 is showing the cross-section of the carbon fiber composite electrode, where the carbon fibers show as dots in the SPE, and the upper and lower bands in the picture are from the microscope testing material. Graphical calculations are made in order to find the volume fraction of fiber for the composite, which was found to be around 8%; verification with matrix burn-off measurements and mass measurements show the same value. This low volume fraction, as well as large internal distances between the fibers in the electrolyte, is limiting both the mechanical properties as well as the electrochemical properties, and needs to be addressed in future research.

Figure 2: Internal characteristics of the carbon fiber composite electrode (cross-section). The white and black dots are carbon fiber ends dispersed in its SPE, and upper and lower bands are the microscope testing material. The lamina thickness is 0.109 mm.

For further mechanical characterization of the carbon fiber composite electrode, tensile tests were performed on manufactured specimens, which contain the identical SPE as used in electrochemical cycling. Tests were performed on unidirectional spread tow composites, with one lamina, in the longitudinal direction and in 20° off-axis to the longitudinal direction. Transverse (90°) specimens were been manufactured but not possible to test, due to the extreme fragility of those specimens.

In the longitudinal direction the elastic modulus (E_1) was found to be 5.6 GPa, which is quite different from the theoretical value from Rule of Mixtures [3], which is calculated to approximately 23.5 GPa. This difference is possibly due to the incomplete adhesion between SPE and carbon fibers inherent in this composite battery setup, and difficulties in tabbing and fixture for the composite testing.

Furthermore, in the 20° off-axis angle, an elastic modulus of 2 GPa was found on average, where the data scatter significantly. The scatter most likely arose because of challenges in producing the off-axis specimens, which similar to the 90° specimens were extremely fragile. Also, when cutting the specimens, cracks were found in the SPE to carbon fiber interface at the edges of the specimen, rendering many specimens unusable. It is likely similar indistinguishable cracks where present in used specimens.

4 CONCLUSION

It is shown that the electrochemical characteristics of the SPE are sufficient to manufacture a functional battery, and at the same time the mechanical properties of the SPE are satisfactory to manufacture an energy-storing composite. With electrochemical cycling it is proven that the carbon fiber composite electrode can store electrical energy, and mechanical testing show sufficient mechanical properties, thus a multifunctional energy-storing composite electrode can be created.

5 FUTURE WORK

Total material efficiency is desired to be improved, for instance, both mechanical and electrochemical properties can be vastly improved by shortening internal distances in the lamina. At the same time, increasing the associated volume fraction of fibers in addition to creating a more homogenous composite would improve not only mechanical properties, but also electrochemical properties. Subsequent research will focus especially on manufacturing methods in order to improve these characteristics, with focus on compaction of the fibers and fiber spreading.

Further research is needed in order to verify mechanical characteristics and engineering constants for the composite, where more accurate mechanical tests are needed on the composite lamina. Especially improved tabbing and fixture for the mechanical testing of the composite electrode is needed.

The interface characteristics between the SPE and the carbon fibers need to be examined in detail. This can be done by further testing of the composite mechanical properties in parallel to the electrochemical testing, and microscopy of the material would be of high interest.

For added validity and generalization of the results, tests will be performed with other carbon fiber types and manufacturers, for instance *Toho Tenax IMS65-E23-24k-830tex* has been proven to work well within a battery cell [1].

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